

Srinivas University

College of Social Sciences and Humanities

From,

Dr. Laveena DMello
Dean and Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

To,

Dr. Meena Montheiro,
Dean & Associate Professor,
School of Social Work,
Roshni Nilaya, Mangaluru- 575001.

Sub: To participate in BOS meeting of CSSH- Course BSW.

Greetings from College of Social Sciences and Humanities!

We would like to request you to participate in our Board of Studies meeting which will be held on **February 3rd Thursday 2022 at 10.30 am** at room no 4, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University. Kindly find the agenda below.

Agenda

1. To Approve the new Course- BSW
2. Identifying the subjects.
3. Value added courses
4. The syllabus as per NEP
5. Rules and regulation
6. Internal and External Paper setters

7. Valuation
8. Any other matter

Your participation will be highly appreciable. Please regulations which we have planned are attached with the NEP is prepared and sent along with this letter. Kindly give your suggestions which are required. So that we can discuss and approve during the meeting. Kindly participate in the meeting.

Thanking you.

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. LaveenaD'Mello
Dean & Professor,
College of Social Sciences and Humanities,
Srinivas University, City Campus,
Pandeshwar, Mangaluru- 575001.

Date: 24th January, 2022

Place: Mangalore

Copy of the letter to;

1. Dr. Pradeep M.D.
2. Dr. Vidya N
3. Dr. Meena Montero
4. Prof. Veena B.K.
5. Dr. Gururaj

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Srinivas University
College of Social Science and Humanities

The report of the Board of Studies of BSW course was conducted on **February 3rd Thursday 2022 at 10.30 am** at room no 4, at College of Social Sciences, Srinivas University.

The following members were present for the meeting

Sl.No.	Name	Designation	Signature
1.	Dr. Laveena D'Mello	Chairperson	
2.	Dr. Pradeep M.D.	Internal Member	
3.	Dr. Vidya N.	Internal Member	
4.	Dr. Meena Monteiro	External Member	
5.	Prof. Veena B.K	External Member	
6.	Dr. Gurur	External Member	

During the meeting the introduction of the course was discussed by Dr. Laveena DMello for the committee. And many issues were discussed. The following resolutions were also taken.
Agenda.

Agenda

1. To Approve the new Course
2. Identifying the subjects.
3. Value added courses
4. The syllabus as per NEP
5. Rules and regulation
6. Internal and External Paper setters
7. Valuation
8. Any other matter

1. **To approve the new Course:** First and foremost the committee have introduced BSW new course this year. And also compared it to existing this year. We already had Master's degree in introducing BSW, we could have first year as Diploma, third year Degree and fourth year Honours. The syllabus and subjects were identified and the whole process started. The syllabus was shared with the committee well in advance. And following resolution were taken.

Resolutions:

- i. The number of credits- 04 Approved.
- ii. Number of Lecture hours- 40 Hours Approved.
- iii. Mode of Delivery- Classroom mode/ Blended Learning/ Networking Based was approved.
- iv. Course objectives- Approved.
- v. Teaching learning process and Pedagogy – and group presentations were Approved.
- vi. Learning Outcome- Approved.
- vii. Course Evaluation- Approved.
- viii. Title -Corrections made and approved.
- ix. Course Code- Approved.

- x. Unit wise division – (Five units each) and course contents- scrutiny done and approved.
- xi. Books for Reference- End of each subject's books were suggested in the syllabus and those were approved.

So complete syllabus was brought to the notice of the board and resolutions were made and approved by the BOS members.

2. **Identifying the subjects:** The various university syllabus was studied and relevant subjects were identified so that there will not be any overlapping of the subjects for Integrated Masters course.

Resolutions: All subjects were studied thoroughly and same was accepted by the BOS. The list of the subject is given below

(Semester scheme attached at the end)

3. **Value added courses:** Value added courses were identified in every semester and same was highlighted in the syllabus.

Resolution: All value added courses semester wise were approved during the meetings

4. The syllabus as per NEP: The new syllabus was drafted as per NEP including all value added

courses, languages, and mode of delivery all was approved.

Resolution: Committee approved the complete syllabus during the meeting.

5. Rules and regulation: There were changes in the Course Regulation Handbook of BSW course with Programme Specific Outcomes (PSOs) and CIP Programmes were shared.

Resolution: Resolution was passed and approved for Programme Specific Outcomes (PO's) Programme Specific Outcomes (Cos) of the BSW Programmes.

6. **Internal and External Paper setters:** The list of paper setters list was proposed during the meeting. The BOS will inform and take their consent by issuing the communication.

Resolution: the list of the members was approved

7. **Internal Assessment:** Outline for continuous assessment the pattern was given.

Resolution: the outline approved in the BOS was as follows

Activities	C1	C2
Session Test	10%	10%
Seminars/Presentations/Activity	10%	
Casestudy/Assignment/Projectwork etc.		10%
Attendance		10%
Total	20%marks	30%marks

At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all subjects of the semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timetable will be followed as per academic calendar.

8. Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of 10 questions all to answer (6 marks), Very short answer three questions (6 marks), Seven marks questions 4 out of 5 questions (28 marks) , and one long answer question (10 marks).

No.of Questions	Type	Question/Marks
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6 out of 6	Objective type	6 x 1 = 06	06
3 out of 4	Very short answer	3 x 2 = 06	06
4 out of 5	Short essay	4 x 7 = 28	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	1 x 10 = 10	10
Total Semester Marks			50

9. **Any other matter:** After the general discussion about the NEP and the process of implementation it was decided to implement syllabus as per NEP. All have to work in hand in hand with other departments in providing the choice base subjects, so that students will benefit maximum. The meeting was ended at 6.00 pm with formal vote of thanks by the chair person Dr. Laveena DMello.

Date:03/02/2022

Place: Mangalore

Subjects' details

II SEMESTER BSW

SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW11	Social Work Methods (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW12	Human Growth and Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BSW14	Field Practicum – II (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BSW17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW18	NSS (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW19	Life Skills (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total				320				750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

III SEMESTER BSW

SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW21	Rural, Urban and Tribal Community (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW22	Counseling and Guidance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BSW24	Field Practicum – III (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BSW27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW28	Games (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW29	Waste Management (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total				320				750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW31	Women And Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW32	NGO and Project Formulation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) E- Business									
4	21BSW34	Field Practicum – IV (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)									
7	21BSW37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

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AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/ Self/ Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW41	Citizen Participation and Local Self Governance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW42	Sociology and Health (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE)Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneurship Development									
4	21BSW44	Field Practicum – V (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW45	Public Relationship (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
7	21BSW47	Case Study on NGO (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW49	Street Play (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
Total						300				750	28

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Courses AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Internal
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			
1	21BSW51	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Honors

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Credits	
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External
1	21BSW61	Social Case work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50
2	21BSW62	Social Group work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50
3	21BSW63	Organizational Psychology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50
4	21BSW64	NGO Case Study 1			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam		Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	
1	21BSW71	Community Organization (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	4
2	21BSW72	Social Action and Social	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	4

		Welfare Administration (DSC)								
3	21BS W73	Gerontological Social Work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	4
4	21BS W74	NGO Case Study 2			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100	16

R.19 Semester wise Subjects details

I SEMESTER BSW SEMESTER I: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW01	Fundamentals of social work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW02	Sociology for Social Workers (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW03 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Early Childhood Development	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW03 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Principles of Management									
4	21BSW04	Field Practicum – I (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW05	Fundamentals of Communication I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW06 K	Kannada I (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW06 H	Hindi I (AECC)									
	21BSW06 M	Malayalam I (AECC)									
	21BSW06 O	Online Mode I (AECC)									
7	21BSW07	Digital Proficiency I (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW08	Health & Wellness (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW09	Basics of Nutrition (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW10	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						300				750	28

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II

SEMESTER BSW SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW11	Social Work Methods (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW12	Human Growth and Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BSW14	Field Practicum – II (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BSW16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BSW17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW18	NSS (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW19	Life Skills (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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III

SEMESTER BSW

SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW21	Rural, Urban and Tribal Community (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW22	Counseling and Guidance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BSW24	Field Practicum – III (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BSW26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BSW27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW28	Games (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW29	Waste Management (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

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SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW31	Women And Development (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW32	NGO and Project Formulation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) E- Business									
4	21BSW34	Field Practicum – IV (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BSW36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)									
	21BSW36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)									
7	21BSW37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BSW40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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SEMESTER V: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW41	Citizen Participation and Local Self Governance (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW42	Sociology and Health (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BSW43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneur ship Development									
4	21BSW44	Field Practicum – V (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BSW45	Public Relationship (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BSW46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
7	21BSW47	Case Study on NGO (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BSW48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BSW49	Street Play (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
Total						300				750	28

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SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW51	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	750	28

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Honors

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW61	Social Case work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW62	Social Group work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW63	Organizational Psychology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BSW64	NGO Case Study 1				200 HRS		350	100	450	16

SEMESTER VIII: Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) Honors

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BSW71	Community Organization (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BSW72	Social Action and Social Welfare Administration (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BSW73	Gerontological Social Work (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BSW74	NGO Case Study 2				200 HRS		350	100	450	16

20. Examination Pattern:

Theory Papers: **Internal Assessment Marks**

Outline for continuous assessment activities for C1 and C2 are as follows:

Activities	C1	C2	Total Marks
Session Test		20	20
Seminars/Presentations/Activity	10		10
Case study /Assignment / Project work etc.		10	15
Attendance		5	5
Total	20 marks	30 marks	50 Marks

At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all the papers to be covered in that semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timings of the examination will be followed as per academic calendar.

21 Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination:

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Objective type questions 6 questions all to answer (6 marks), Very short answer three questions out of four questions (6 marks) Seven marks questions 4 out of 5 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 10 marks out of two (10 marks).

No. of	Type	Question/Marks	Total Marks
6 out of 6	Objective type	6 x 1 = 06	06
3 out of 4	Very short	3 x 2 = 06	06
4 out of 5	Short essay	4 x 7 = 28	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	1 x 10 = 10	10
Total Semester Marks			50
